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Digital Twin-aided Orchestration of Mobile Edge Computing with Grant-free Access

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Abstract—In this work, digital twin-aided edge computing is investigated, where each user utilizes grant-free random access with adaptive rate, in order to offload their task to the edge server, by exploiting a novel probabilistic partial offloading scheme. Each device is assumed to have an infinite buffer to store its tasks. The aim of the proposed work is to minimize the average delay of the partial offloading. To that end, the average delay of waiting in the queue, the delay of offloading, and the local computation delay are extracted by using standard queuing theory tools. Then, the resulting non-convex problem of minimizing the average delay of all clients is formulated. In order to deal with the increased complexity of this problem, successive convex approximation (SCA), alternating optimization (AO), and various algebraic manipulations are utilized to obtain an equivalent convex problem, whose solution is tractable. Finally, simulation results are presented to showcase the value of the proposed analysis and offer important insights into the proposed DT-aided edge network. Notably, the proposed partial offloading scheme is found to be much more robust compared to both local computing and full offloading, especially when the density of the network increases.

Index Terms—grant-free random access, 6G, mobile edge computing, digital twin

I. INTRODUCTION

NEXT-GENERATION smart Internet of Things (IoT) networks are predicted to rely on smart devices where edge intelligence and computing can be fully realized at the devices, e.g., smartphones, vehicles, machines, and robots [1], [2]. Such a device-centric network poses new challenges and requirements on the design and operation of its wireless communications, since smart devices will not only generate or exploit data but will also actively join the network management and operation processes [1], [2]. Moreover, the large number of potentially active devices complicates resource

allocation a priori, therefore several works have studied various contention-based protocols, in order to avoid that too many resources remain idle due to intermittent traffic [3], [4].

Toward reducing the access delay for IoT networks, the 3rd generation partnership project (3GPP) in Release 16 of the 5th generation new radio (5G NR) proposed a two-step random access scheme which is able to further reduce the signal overhead [5]. The main idea behind grant-free (GF) access is that an active device does not wait for a response from the BS after transmitting its preamble (1st step), and immediately transmits its data packet (2nd step). Therefore, the handshaking process between the user and the base station is avoided, consequently reducing the associated signalling overhead. The key challenge for GF transmissions is contention, as multiple users may choose to transmit at the same channel resources at the same time.

However, future networks as they are shaped by the sixth-generation (6G) concept [6] will need to support novel use cases, for example, virtual, augmented, and extended reality (VR/AR/XR), tactile Internet, intelligent power grids and smart cities [1], [2], [7]. Those use cases will require scalable wireless sensor networks, but they will also demand intensive computing and medium-high data rates [1], [7]. In 6G systems, in contrast to cloud architectures, which enhance the efficiency of intensive data computation by using centralized processing, intelligent functionalities will be extended to the network edge, thanks to the computational capabilities of the edge nodes, thanks to the convergence of artificial intelligence (AI), communications, and edge computation [1]. Thus, edge computing [8] architectures will provide intelligence physically closer to the end users [8]. That can significantly improve the end-to-end latency, especially for users who repeatedly tend to offload intensive tasks to the server.

Furthermore, edge computing can be combined with the emerging technology of digital twins (DTs), in order to enhance the performance of wireless communication systems towards the 6G era. A DT is a comprehensive software representation of an individual physical object or system, that includes its real-life properties, conditions and behaviours [9]. By combining mobile edge computing (MEC) and DT, the

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MEC server status and the status of the end devices, such as the distance of the end users from the MEC server, the average task arrival at the users' buffers or the CPU frequency at the edge servers can be directly transferred to the network's orchestrator. Then, based on that knowledge, the orchestrator provides the physical network with intelligent and optimal decisions [9]. Therefore, the DT's goal is to capture the physical features of the network, while the orchestrator's aim is to develop an optimal strategy based on those features. Due to the fact the a DT continuously evolves, alongside its physical entity, it provides the orchestrator with an improved view of the underlying physical network.

A. Literature Review

GF transmission schemes have gained considerable attention recently [3]–[5], [10]–[14]. In [4], [10] the concept of GFRA was thoroughly presented for massive MTC and URLLC use cases, while its combination with semi-GF based on non-orthogonal multiple access (NOMA) was discussed in [11]. Furthermore, GF-NOMA was investigated in [13] and [15]. In [3], two reliability-enhancing solutions were proposed for GFRA aided URLLC applications. The first proposes re-transmissions over shared resources, whereas the second proposal incorporates GF-NOMA with overlapping transmissions being resolved through the use of advanced receivers. Moreover, in [12], URLLC with multiple grants was designed. Finally, in [14], the success probability of GFRA with massive multi-input multi-output (MIMO) was examined.

MEC has been also extensively studied in the recent past, often by taking into account congestion occurring at the buffers of the users or at the buffers of the MEC server [16]–[26]. However, the state of the art on MEC cannot be generalized for GF transmissions, since continuous-time queueing models are adopted. For example, in [16], the M/M/c/c queueing system was exploited and a holistic QoS-aware framework for Industrial IoT systems is designed, whereas in [17] a heuristic scheduling model was designed to maximize the offloading energy and execution efficiency of an Erlang queueing MEC system. Similarly, in [27] three Erlang based queueing models were applied, one at the mobile users, one at the edge server and one at the cloud server. Moreover, the delay of a MEC serving multi-class users, based on continuous-time queueing, was studied in [18], while in [20] a closed-form multi-level water-filling computation offloading solution was proposed in order to characterize the influence of remote queue state information to the average delay. Furthermore, in [21], a distributed task offloading scheme is investigated with consideration of the upper layer queueing dynamics and the lower-layer coupled wireless interference. Also, in [25], a stochastic buffer-aided relay-assisted MEC was examined.

A similar framework is proposed in [28], in which a cross-layer MEC design is studied for URLLC-eMBB services with short packet transmissions. The delay of the system is examined, however, the duration of the data transmission slot and partial offloading are not considered, while the channel access is not GF-aided. Furthermore, in [29], the aim is to minimize the users' power consumption under partial offloading, while

statistical constraints are imposed on task queue lengths by applying extreme value theory. Moreover, in [30], a deep reinforcement learning algorithm was designed to study the joint optimization of task offloading for a MEC system with application to AR. In addition, in [31], resource allocation was investigated for URLLC vehicular edge computing, while in [32] the trade-off between latency and reliability in URLLC MEC was examined.

Recently, several studies have also aimed on designing DTs combined with MEC servers [9], [33]–[38] where the MEC-DT concept is utilised to extract optimal network orchestration strategies in real-time. For instance, in [33]–[36], deep reinforcement learning (DRL)-based algorithms were proposed to train the DT of the MEC network for making offloading decisions, edge association, resource allocation, increasing the energy efficiency and reducing the migration cost. In addition to this, [37] and [38] exploit the DT of a MEC system to minimise the end-to-end latency, by also considering the deviations of the DT edge server with the true values of its state. Moreover, in [9] a secure and latency-aware edge computing architecture was designed. However, none of the aforementioned works on DT-aided MEC study the integration of DT and MEC for GF access schemes, nor take into account the delay caused by the devices' buffers.

B. Motivation and Contributions

Inspired by the above as well as the advantages of DT-aided edge computing and GF access protocols, this work aims to combine DT-aided MEC with grant-free access. To the authors' best knowledge, this is the first work that proposes DT-aided edge computing with GF access and partial offloading. Next-generation IoT's role will be to improve intelligence in physical systems, such as smart cities, transportation and power grids by monitoring their unique characteristics [1], [2]. Those data will then be processed, either locally, or by the edge in order to improve the system's intelligence. Since IoT devices produce tasks sporadically, they do not need to access the wireless medium constantly. Moreover, the great number of IoT devices makes scheduling rather impossible, since wireless resources are limited to stay idle due to intermittent traffic. Thus, GF access is a strong candidate to enable the communication between next-generation IoTs and the MEC server.

Moreover, the majority of the existing literature on MEC or DT-aided MEC, considers the partial offloading as a procedure which splits the size of a task into two parts, which in practice may not be straightforward to implement, since separating a task into smaller subtasks depends on the task's structure and functions. In our analysis, a task is either transmitted to the MEC, or it is locally processed, as shown in Fig. 2, which offers lower implementation complexity and is more appropriate for next-generation IoT. Therefore, the proposed partial scheme is a probabilistic binary offloading scheme, which adjusts the ratio of the tasks transmitted to the MEC server and the number of the tasks processed locally, according to the channel conditions, the density of the network, the available preambles, etc. Furthermore, in contrast to the state

Fig. 1: The proposed DT-aided architecture

of the art on discrete-time queuing theory, where instant packet transmissions on error-free channels are assumed, in our analysis, an error-prone channel is considered, while the data transmission duration is also optimized. The contributions of the paper are summarized below:

- A DT-aided MEC system with GFRA is designed under a novel partial offloading. The partial binary offloading is a probabilistic binary offloading scheme, that can be visualized as a switch, which with probability θ sends a packet to the transmission buffer and with $1 - \theta$ probability sends a packet to the local computing buffer, as in Fig. 2. Moreover, closed-form delay expressions are extracted, under the assumption of infinity buffer capacity. In contrast to the state of the art on discrete-time queuing theory, error-prone channel conditions are studied, while the transmission delay is also considered.
- The average delay until a task is processed, either locally or by the MEC server, is minimized. Moreover, the data transmission phase duration is also optimized. It should also be noted that the formulated optimization problem can be easily modified so that the devices' power consumption is minimized, subjected to delay constraints. For solving the non-convex delay minimization problem, an efficient algorithm is proposed, which utilizes successive convex approximation (SCA) and alternating optimization (AO).
- Finally, numerical results illustrate the superiority of the proposed scheme. Moreover, insights about the DT-aided MEC network are extracted, while the convergence of the proposed optimization algorithm is illustrated.

C. Structure

In section II, the proposed system model is introduced. In section III, a brief stability analysis is presented for the buffers. In section IV, the delay analysis for the buffers is demonstrated, while in section V, the computation model of the DT is presented. In section VI, the delay minimization

Fig. 2: Partial offloading diagram

problem is formulated and solved. In section VII, numerical results are shown and different insights are discussed. Finally, in section VIII a conclusion is drawn.

II. SYSTEM MODEL

We consider a DT-empowered MEC server-client system model which consists of N devices and one MEC server, as shown in Fig. 1. The architecture relies on two layers, the physical layer and the DT layer. The physical layer consists of all the physical components of the network, such as devices, edge servers, base stations, while also taking into account each component's limitations regarding the hardware, the transmission power etc. Each device lies in a distance d_m and employs GFRA to communicate with the server and to transmit computationally expensive tasks. The communication between the users and the MEC server is separated into two phases, a preamble phase and a data transmission phase. The preamble phase duration is much shorter than the data phase duration, while the available number of preambles is denoted as L_p . The preambles are orthogonal, therefore a collision between the users can only happen during the preamble phase. A user that is active, uniformly chooses one of the available preambles and transmits it to the MEC server. Then, immediately, the user enters the data transmission phase, without waiting for a response from the MEC server. The access probability, i.e., the probability that a user becomes active and gets access to the channel is defined as q_k . Also, let P_t^k represent the transmission power of the data transmission phase. Due to the fact that a user is not always active, the total number of active users is unknown.

Moreover, a device has the ability to perform basic computation itself and hence a full offloading is not mandatory. We assume that each device k generates tasks at the rate of λ_k tasks per second, where each task has a size of L_k bits. Also, the devices' computing capabilities are described by their processors' CPU cycles per second, f_k . Each task is described by its size and a required number of CPU cycles per bit, X_k . The splitting factor $\theta_k \in [0, 1]$ represents the percentage of the tasks which are transmitted to the MEC server and thus, $1 - \theta_k$ represents the percentage of the tasks that will be computed locally. We assume that each device has a buffer in order to store its generated tasks. Since the devices utilize a partial offloading strategy, it is convenient to assume that the storage capability of the devices is separated into two buffers, one for the tasks that are waiting to be

transmitted to the MEC server and one for the tasks that are in line to be computed locally. Both buffers are considered to have infinite capacity. Practically, tasks cannot be afforded to be lost, therefore the assumption of an infinite buffer is meaningful. However, our analysis can also be modified for the case of finite buffers, which is one of our future goals. Each buffer can be described by a queue with an average input data rate and an average output data rate.

The DT layer is an exact replica of the underlying physical layer which takes into account all the hardware components of the physical devices and the network topology. The DT interacts with the physical layer in order to gather data which aid to improve the digital representation of the physical world and capture physical changes in real-time. Based on the information provided by the DT, an orchestrator efficiently manages the networks' available resources. Specific communication resources can be devoted for the communication between the DT and its physical replica, such as specific frequency bands, or specific time slots. Nonetheless, the communication may be susceptible to great overhead and delay. Therefore, an older version of the physical entity can be used, to compensate for possible delays during DT updating. Furthermore, due to the fact that the networks' devices operate under specific settings, the optimal resource allocation provided by the orchestrator may deviate from the actual allocation strategy followed by the users. That, along with the wireless channel limitations can introduce errors in the DT representation, whose impact is shown in the numerical results section.

The DT of the physical layer is represented as $DT = \{(\mathcal{M}, \hat{\mathcal{M}}), (\mathcal{N}, \hat{\mathcal{N}})\}$, including the MEC server and the N users. Without loss of generality, it is assumed that the DT of the MEC server is perfect due to the superiority of the wired backhaul channels. The DT of the m -th user is denoted as $DT_m = \{(\mathcal{N}, \hat{\mathcal{N}})\}$. $\hat{\mathcal{N}}$ is the set containing all the parameters and variables describing the physical users. As in [37], in this paper, a deviation n of available CPU frequency is used to describe the deviation between real users and their digital counterparts, which can be either positive or negative. Moreover, a deviation can also be used to describe the imperfect knowledge of the DT regarding the localization of the devices, their hardware configuration. The deviation n is also assumed known in advance [37], however the case of a stochastic deviation can also be studied. The following assumptions hold in our analysis:

- The channel is not error-free. A packet can be lost either due to a collision during the preamble phase or due to an outage event caused by the channel's conditions during the data transmission phase.
- The preamble phase duration is negligible compared to the data phase duration, due to the preambles' small size. Therefore, the data transmission phase approximately captures the whole duration of a time slot, which equals τ seconds. Due to synchronization issues, the time slot duration is equal for all users in the system and the duration of the time slot is limited by the worst user or the user with the biggest task [4].
- A packet that failed to be transmitted, will be retransmitted at the next time slot with the same probability q_k . Also,

the failure or the success of a packet is considered known instantly.

- Tasks are generated with an average rate of λ_k tasks per second. The communication time is divided into time slots of duration τ , therefore, a task is equivalently modelled to be generated at the end of a time slot with probability λ_k^* , and no task is generated with probability $1 - \lambda_k^*$. From [39], the following holds

$$\lambda_k = \frac{\lambda_k^*}{\tau}. \quad (1)$$

Since $0 \leq \lambda_k^* \leq 1$, it needs to hold that $\tau \leq \frac{1}{\lambda_k} \forall k$.

- Regarding the GF transmissions, a task departs from the queue at the beginning of a time slot, with the assumption that only one task departs at a slot. Note, that a late arrival model is adopted, and so, a task arrives just before the departure of a task.
- During partial offloading, a task's size is not altered, but the task is either computed locally or it is transmitted to the MEC server as a whole. The partial factor θ_k expresses the percentage of tasks that are transmitted to the MEC server. Therefore, $\theta_k \lambda_k$ tasks per second enter the transmission buffer and $(1 - \theta_k) \lambda_k$ tasks per second enter the CPU buffer. Since $0 \leq \theta_k \leq 1$ that can equivalently be considered as probabilistic partial scheme, where with θ_k probability a task is sent to the MEC server, otherwise it is locally processed. It should be noted that this offloading offers lower implementation complexity compared to the usual partial offloading, since separating a task into subtasks is not straightforward and depends on the task's structure, content and functions.

The average throughput (bits/sec) of the proposed GF transmission, under Rayleigh fading conditions and for one available preamble, is given by [40] as

$$\bar{R}_k = R_k \exp\left(-\frac{(2^{R_k} - 1)N_0}{P_k \Omega_k}\right) q_k \prod_{i \neq k} (1 - q_i), \quad (2)$$

where R_k is the fixed data rate (bits/sec) of each device and Ω_k denotes the path loss between the k -th device and the MEC server. For convenience, in our mathematical analysis we set $\Omega_k = 1$. The second term, from the left, of (2) expresses the probability of non-outage probability during the data phase, assuming a Rayleigh channel. The last term, from the left, of (2) is the probability of no-collision during the preamble phase, for the case of one preamble. The probability of no-collision, for L_p available preambles, can easily be found [14] as

$$q_k \prod_{i \neq k} \left(1 - \frac{q_i}{L_p}\right). \quad (3)$$

Also, the power consumption due to local computation is given as [8],

$$P_{cmp} = k_k f_k^3, \quad (4)$$

where k_k is a constant related to the hardware architecture.

Fig. 3: Probability flow chart of the transmission buffer

III. DELAY ANALYSIS

A. Delay analysis of the GFRA buffer

We consider a GFRA scheme where each user has an infinite buffer capacity and a discrete-time queueing model. The analysis of the queue can be carried out similarly to [41]. The total probability flow through any closed boundary must be zero, so for the k -th user according to Fig. 3, the following needs to hold,

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda'_k g_{0,k} &= \mu_k (1 - \lambda'_k) g_{1,k}, \\ \lambda'_k (1 - \mu_k) g_{i,k} &= \mu_k (1 - \lambda'_k) g_{i+1,k}, \quad i \in Z \quad (5) \\ \lambda'_k (1 - \mu_k) g_{K-1,k} &= \mu_k g_{K,k}, \end{aligned}$$

where $g_{i,k}$ denotes the probability that the buffer of the k -th user contains i tasks. The probability that a task will arrive to the transmission queue, following (1), is given as

$$\lambda'_k = \theta_k \lambda_k \tau. \quad (6)$$

Also, μ_k is the probability of successful transmission of the k -th user and for a GFRA scheme with imperfect channel conditions, is given by (2) as,

$$\mu_k = \exp\left(-\frac{(2^{R_k} - 1)N_0}{P_k \Omega_k}\right) q_k \prod_{i \neq k} \left(1 - \frac{q_i}{L_p}\right). \quad (7)$$

From (5) all $g_{i,k}$, $i \in Z$, can be calculated with respect to $g_{0,k}$ as,

$$\begin{aligned} g_{i,k} &= \left(\frac{\lambda'_k (1 - \mu_k)}{\mu_k (1 - \lambda'_k)}\right)^{i-1} \frac{\lambda'_k}{\mu_k (1 - \lambda'_k)} g_{0,k}, \quad i \in Z \\ g_{K,k} &= \frac{\lambda'_k}{\mu_k} \left(\frac{\lambda'_k (1 - \mu_k)}{\mu_k (1 - \lambda'_k)}\right)^{K-1} g_{0,k} \end{aligned} \quad (8)$$

Substituting (8) into the total probability law

$$\sum_{i=0}^K g_{i,k} = 1$$

we have

$$\begin{aligned} g_{0,k} &= \left(\frac{\mu_k}{\mu_k - \lambda'_k} - \frac{\lambda_k'^2}{\mu_k (\mu_k - \lambda'_k)} \frac{\lambda'_k}{\mu_k} \left(\frac{\lambda'_k (1 - \mu_k)}{\mu_k (1 - \lambda'_k)}\right)^{K-1}\right)^{-1} \\ &= 1 - \rho_k, \quad \text{for } K \rightarrow \infty, \end{aligned} \quad (9)$$

where $\rho_k = \lambda'_k / \mu_k$. Now that $g_{0,k}$ is known, every $g_{i,k}$ can be calculated using (5). Furthermore, the average queue length of the k -th user can be found as [41],

$$E_k(l) = \sum_{i=0}^K i g_{i,k}$$

and for an infinite buffer, i.e. $K \rightarrow \infty$, by [41] we have

$$E_k(l) = \frac{\rho_k (1 - \lambda'_k)}{1 - \rho_k}.$$

Hence, using Little's law [41] the average response time, in seconds, is given as,

$$d_{q,k} = \frac{E_k(l)}{\lambda'_k} \tau = \frac{(1 - \lambda'_k)}{\mu_k (1 - \rho_k)} \tau = \frac{(1 - \lambda'_k)}{(\mu_k - \lambda'_k)} \tau. \quad (10)$$

Note that the average response time is defined as the duration from the moment a packet enters the queue until its successful departure.

B. Delay analysis of the local computation buffer

The local computation buffer is also assumed infinite and there is no need for retransmission mechanisms at the output of the CPU buffer. The CPU buffer acts in a deterministic way, therefore it can be modelled as a Geo/D/1 queue [39]. Its average departure rate is then given as

$$\bar{\mu}_k = \frac{f_k}{X_k L_k} \tau \quad (\text{tasks/slot}). \quad (11)$$

The average input rate is given as $\bar{\lambda}_k = (1 - \theta_k) \lambda_k \tau$. The Geo/D/1 queueing delay is known and given from [39], in seconds, as,

$$\tilde{d}_{cq} = \frac{\bar{\rho}_k}{2(1 - \bar{\rho}_k)} \left(\frac{1}{\bar{\mu}_k} - 1\right) \tau, \quad (12)$$

where $\bar{\rho}_k = \frac{\bar{\lambda}_k}{\bar{\mu}_k}$. Note that the queueing delay measures the delay spent until a task reaches the end of the queue and begins to be served by the CPU.

IV. STABILITY ANALYSIS

A queueing system is said to be unstable if the queue size goes to infinity with non-zero probability. Hence, stability analysis makes sense only for queueing systems with infinite buffer capacity. In this section, we study the stability of the proposed buffer architecture with infinite buffer capacity. From [41] an infinite buffer system is global stable if and only if its mean input data rate is equal or less than its mean output data rate. For the buffer of the k -th device, which is dedicated to full offloading stability is provided when it holds that

$$\mu_k \geq \lambda'_k. \quad (13)$$

Moreover, when a packet successfully leaves the queue, all of its bits are pushed to the MEC server. That requires a time duration, which has to be less than the duration of the data transmission phase of one time slot. Otherwise, the next packet in queue of any user may suffer an unnecessary collision in the next time slot, since by assumption all packets are transmitted

to the beginning of the data transmission phase. Thus, the following has to hold

$$\frac{L_k}{R_k} \leq \tau. \quad (14)$$

Note that with (14), an adaptive rate is introduced to the GFRA transmission, which is in contrast to the existing literature where it is assumed that a packet is transmitted instantly. On the other hand, for the buffer dedicated to local computing to be global stable, it is required to hold that

$$\bar{\mu}_k \geq \bar{\lambda}_k. \quad (15)$$

It should be noted that a system which can perform partial offloading is more flexible and stable than a system which performs binary offloading, since utilizing partial offloading means $\theta \leq 1$, therefore each buffer experiences less congestion in comparison to the case of full offloading or local computing. Moreover, the stability constraints have to be taken into account for any optimization problem, otherwise the optimal solution of the problem might lead to an unstable solution and huge queueing delays.

V. COMPUTATION MODEL OF PHYSICAL AND DT COUNTERPARTS

The computation latency until a task of L_k bits is processed when a physical device's CPU operates with frequency of f_k is known and given as

$$\tilde{d}_{cmp,k} = \frac{L_k X_k}{f_k} \quad (16)$$

The DT of the k -th device is expressed as $DT_k = \{(f_k, \tilde{f}_k)\}$, where $\tilde{f}_k = f_k + n_k$ is the estimated frequency at the DT and n_k is the frequency deviation between the virtual representation and its k -th physical counterpart. Assuming that the deviation of the CPU processing frequency between the physical devices and their DT can be acquired in advance [37], the computing latency gap between the real value and the DT estimation can be calculated as [37]

$$d_{gap,k} = -L_k X_k \frac{n_k}{f_k(f_k + n_k)}, \quad (17)$$

therefore the total computation latency estimated at the DT is given as

$$d_{cmp,k} = \tilde{d}_{cmp} + d_{gap} = \frac{L_k X_k}{f_k + n_k} \quad (18)$$

It is also assumed, that the DT has perfect knowledge of the MEC's condition, which can be justified by the superiority of the wired backhaul channels. By following a similar approach, the queueing delay at the devices' buffers is estimated at the DT as

$$d_{cq,k} = \frac{\tilde{\rho}_k}{2(1 - \tilde{\rho}_k)} \left(\frac{1}{\tilde{\mu}_k} - 1 \right) \tau, \quad (19)$$

where $\tilde{\mu}_k = \frac{f_k + n_k}{X_k L_k} \tau$ and $\tilde{\rho}_k = \frac{\tilde{\lambda}_k}{\tilde{\mu}_k}$

VI. DELAY MINIMIZATION

A. Problem Formulation

We aim to minimize the average delay of every device while taking into account their power and stability requirements. To that end, both resource scheduling is required, so as to provide a certain amount of predictability in the available resources and high reliability, as well as probabilistic access, in order to avoid that too many resources remain idle, due to the users not being active constantly. Therefore, the access probability q_k , the offloading factor θ_k and the data transmission duration will be optimized according to the total number of devices in the system, the average channel statistics, and the average task generation rate of each device. Note that the proposed problem also provides a lower bound of the delay when the activation probability q_k is fixed or unknown. Furthermore, the formulated analysis can also be adjusted for a power consumption minimization problem subject to delay constraints. The average delay between the k -th user and the MEC server is given as

$$d_k = d_{q,k} + d_{t,k} + d_{mec,k}, \quad (20)$$

where $d_{t,k}$ expresses the delay caused when a task successfully leaves the queue until all of its bits are pushed to the MEC server and is given as,

$$d_{t,k} = \frac{L_k}{R_k}. \quad (21)$$

The computation time of the MEC server and the delay caused during the downlink communication between the MEC and its clients is denoted as $d_{mec,k}$ and it is omitted since the MEC server has superior capabilities compared to the devices it serves. Similarly, the average local computation delay of every device is given as,

$$d_{l,k} = d_{cmp,k} + d_{cq,k}, \quad (22)$$

Thus, the overall average delay until a task of the k -th device is completed, either at the MEC server or locally, is given as,

$$d_{a,k} = (1 - \theta_k) d_{l,k} + \theta_k d_k. \quad (23)$$

Therefore, the proposed delay minimization problem with power constraints can be formulated as follows,

$$\begin{aligned} & \min_{\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{q}, \tilde{\mathbf{f}}, \boldsymbol{\tau}, \mathbf{P}^t} \sum_{k=1}^N [(1 - \theta_k) d_{l,k} + \theta_k d_k] \\ \text{s.t. } & C_1 : P_k^t + k_k \tilde{f}_k^3 \leq P_{\max,k}, \quad \forall k \in \mathbb{N} \\ & C_2 : \frac{L_k}{R_k} \leq \tau \\ & C_3 : \mu_k \geq \lambda'_k \\ & C_4 : \bar{\mu}_k \geq \bar{\lambda}_k \end{aligned} \quad (24)$$

where $\tilde{f}_k = f_k + n_k$. Constraint C_1 limits the transmission power during the uplink communication using GFRA and the power consumed during the local computing, so that every device is power efficient. Constraints C_2 - C_4 ensure that the optimal solution of the proposed problem is also stable.

B. Convex Transformation

The problem is non-convex due to its non-convex objective function and constraints $C_2 - C_4$ containing the product of various optimization variables. In order to formulate it as a convex problem we first transform it into its epigraph form as follows,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min_{\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{q}, \tilde{\mathbf{f}}, \boldsymbol{\tau}, \boldsymbol{\tau}_k, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}, \mathbf{P}^t} \sum_{k=1}^N \tau_k \\
\text{s.t. } & C_1 : P_k^t + k_k \tilde{f}_k^3 \leq P_{\max, k}, \quad \forall k \in \mathbb{N} \\
& C_2 : \frac{L_k}{R_k} \leq \tau \\
& C_3 : \mu_k \geq \lambda'_k \\
& C_4 : \bar{\mu}_k \geq \bar{\lambda}_k \\
& C_5 : (1 - \theta_k) d_{1, k} \leq \tau_k \\
& C_6 : \theta_k d_k \leq \tau_k.
\end{aligned} \tag{25}$$

The problem is still non-convex. By substituting the relations for $\bar{\mu}_k$, λ'_k , $\bar{\lambda}_k$, d_k and $d_{\text{local}, k}$, problem (25) is equivalently written as,

$$\min_{\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{q}, \tilde{\mathbf{f}}, \boldsymbol{\tau}, \boldsymbol{\tau}_k, \mathbf{P}^t} \sum_{k=1}^N \tau_k \tag{26}$$

$$\text{s.t. } C_1 : P_k^t + k_k \tilde{f}_k^3 \leq P_{\max, k}, \quad \forall k \in \mathbb{N} \tag{27}$$

$$C_2 : \frac{L_k}{R_k} \leq \tau \tag{28}$$

$$C_3 : \mu_k \geq \lambda_k \theta_k \tau \tag{29}$$

$$C_4 : \frac{\tilde{f}_k}{X_k L_k} \geq (1 - \theta_k) \lambda_k \tag{30}$$

$$C_5 : (1 - \theta_k) \frac{X_k L_k}{\tilde{f}_k} + \tag{31}$$

$$\frac{(1 - \theta_k)^2 \lambda_k}{2 \left(\frac{\tilde{f}_k}{X_k L_k} - (1 - \theta_k) \lambda_k \right)} \left(\frac{X_k L_k}{\tilde{f}_k} - \tau \right) \leq \tau_k \tag{32}$$

$$C_6 : \theta_k \frac{L_k}{R_k} + \theta_k \frac{(1 - \lambda_k \theta_k \tau)}{(\mu_k - \lambda_k \theta_k \tau)} \tau \leq \tau_k \tag{33}$$

$$\tag{34}$$

Problem (26) is non-convex, due to μ_k containing the product of several optimization variables, as well because of the constraints C_2 - C_6 . To formulate the problem as convex we will introduce the following auxiliary variable

$$\tilde{\mu}_k \geq \mu_k. \tag{35}$$

One way to deal with the product of optimization variables in C_2 - C_6 is to take the logarithm of both sides of those constraints. However, due to the summation in the left side of constraints C_5 and C_6 , those constraints will be difficult to handle. To that end, the variables $\tau_k^{(i)}$, $i \in \{1, 2, 3, 4\}$ will be introduced, for which it holds that

$$\tau_k^{(1)} + \tau_k^{(2)} \leq \tau_k \quad \text{and} \quad \tau_k^{(3)} + \tau_k^{(4)} \leq \tau_k. \tag{36}$$

Utilizing the above formulations, problem (26) is written as,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min_{\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{q}, \tilde{\mathbf{f}}, \boldsymbol{\tau}, \boldsymbol{\tau}_k, \tilde{\boldsymbol{\mu}}, \mathbf{P}^t} \sum_{k=1}^N \tau_k \\
\text{s.t. } & C_1 : P_k^t + k_k \tilde{f}_k^3 \leq P_{\max, k}, \quad \forall k \in \mathbb{N} \\
& C_2 : \frac{L_k}{R_k} \leq \tau \\
& C_3 : \tilde{\mu}_k \geq \lambda_k \theta_k \tau \\
& C_4 : \frac{\tilde{f}_k}{X_k L_k} \geq (1 - \theta_k) \lambda_k \\
& C_5 : (1 - \theta_k) \frac{X_k L_k}{\tilde{f}_k} \leq \tau_k^{(1)} \\
& C_6 : \frac{(1 - \theta_k)^2 \lambda_k}{2 \left(\frac{\tilde{f}_k}{X_k L_k} - (1 - \theta_k) \lambda_k \right)} \left(\frac{X_k L_k}{\tilde{f}_k} - \tau \right) \leq \tau_k^{(2)} \\
& C_7 : \theta_k \frac{L_k}{R_k} \leq \tau_k^{(3)} \\
& C_8 : \theta_k \frac{(1 - \lambda_k \theta_k \tau)}{(\tilde{\mu}_k - \lambda_k \theta_k \tau)} \tau \leq \tau_k^{(4)} \\
& C_9 : \tau_k^{(1)} + \tau_k^{(2)} = \tau_k \\
& C_{10} : \tau_k^{(3)} + \tau_k^{(4)} = \tau_k \\
& C_{11} : \exp \left(-\frac{(2^{R_k} - 1) N_0}{P_k \Omega_k} \right) q_k \prod_{i \neq k} \left(1 - \frac{q_i}{L_p} \right) \geq \tilde{\mu}_k
\end{aligned} \tag{37}$$

Problem (37) is still non-convex. From constraint C_2 and relations (1), (12) it is concluded that the time slot duration τ is lower bounded by the value of $\max \left\{ \frac{L_k}{R_k} \right\}$ and it is upper bounded by the lowest value of $\min \left\{ \frac{1}{\lambda_k} \right\}$ and $\min \left\{ \frac{X_k L_k}{\tilde{f}_k} \right\}$. Therefore the following has to hold,

$$\max_k \left\{ \frac{L_k}{R_k} \right\} \leq \min_k \left\{ \frac{1}{\lambda_k}, \frac{X_k L_k}{\tilde{f}_k} \right\}. \tag{38}$$

Otherwise, the problem is either infeasible, due to (1) and (12), or collisions occur between two packets sent to different time slots due to C_2 . To make the problem simpler to solve, the concept of AO will be utilized, by fixing the value of τ when optimizing the rest of the variables, while the optimal value of τ will be given as

$$\tau^* = \max_k \left\{ \frac{L_k}{R_k^*} \right\}. \tag{39}$$

To deal with the non-convex constraints, the logarithm of both sides of constraints C_5 - C_8 and C_{11} will be taken.

Consequently, the problem is formulated as follows,

$$\begin{aligned}
& \min_{\mathbf{R}, \mathbf{q}, \tilde{f}, \tau_k, \mathbf{P}^t} \sum_{k=1}^N \tau_k \\
& \text{s.t. } (37). C_1, C_2, C_3, C_4, C_9, C_{10} \\
& C_5 : \log\left(\frac{\tilde{f}_k}{X_k L_k}\right) + \log(\tau_k^{(1)}) + \log(1 - \theta_{k,0}) + \frac{(\theta_k - \theta_{k,0})}{\theta_{k,0}} \leq 0 \\
& C_6 : \log\left(\frac{X_k L_k}{\tilde{f}_{k,0}} - \tau\right) - \frac{\tilde{f}_k - \tilde{f}_{k,0}}{\tilde{f}_{k,0} X_k L_k - \tau \tilde{f}_{k,0}} \\
& \quad + 2 \log(1 - \theta_{k,0}) - 2 \frac{\theta_k - \theta_{k,0}}{1 - \theta_{k,0}} \\
& \quad - \log\left(\frac{\tilde{f}_k}{X_k L_k} - (1 - \theta_k) \lambda_k\right) + \log\left(\frac{\lambda_k}{2}\right) - \log(\tau_k^{(2)}) \leq 0 \\
& C_7 : -\log\left(\frac{R_k}{L_k}\right) - \log(\tau_k^{(3)}) + \log(\theta_{k,0}) + \frac{\theta_k - \theta_{k,0}}{\theta_{k,0}} \leq 0 \\
& C_8 : -\log(\tilde{\mu}_k - \lambda_k \theta_k \tau) + \log(\tau) - \log(\tau_k^{(4)}) \log(\theta_{k,0}) \\
& \quad + \frac{\theta_k - \theta_{k,0}}{\theta_{k,0}} + \log(1 - \lambda_k \theta_k \tau) - \lambda_k \tau \frac{\theta_k - \theta_{k,0}}{1 - \lambda_k \tau \theta_{k,0}} \leq 0 \\
& C_{11} : \frac{(2^{R_k} - 1) N_0}{P_k \Omega_k} - \log(q_k) - \sum_{i \neq k} \log\left(1 - \frac{q_i}{L_p}\right) \\
& \quad - \log(\tilde{\mu}_{k,0}) - \frac{\tilde{\mu}_k - \tilde{\mu}_{k,0}}{\tilde{\mu}_{k,0}} \leq 0
\end{aligned} \tag{40}$$

where in order to cope with the non-convex negative logarithmic terms of constraints C_2 , C_3 , $C_6 - C_8$ and C_{11} , that occurred due to taking the logarithm of both sides, SCA was exploited. Specifically, each negative logarithmic term was approximated by its first order Taylor approximation. In [42] three conditions are mentioned that are required to hold when approximating a non-convex constraint. Assume that $\gamma(x)$ is the non-convex term and $\tilde{\gamma}(x, x_k)$ is its convex approximation. Then the following need to hold,

$$(i) \quad \gamma(x) \leq \tilde{\gamma}(x, x_k) \tag{41}$$

$$(ii) \quad \gamma(x_k) = \tilde{\gamma}(x_k, x_k) \tag{42}$$

$$(iii) \quad \frac{\partial \gamma(x_k)}{\partial x} = \frac{\partial \tilde{\gamma}(x_k, x_k)}{\partial x}. \tag{43}$$

It can be easily verified that for the $\log(\cdot)$ function and its Taylor approximation all three conditions hold. Eventually, problem (40) is convex. Furthermore, it should be noted that the formulated average delay minimization problem can be easily written as a power consumption minimization problem subject to average delay constraints. Specifically, by fixing the values of τ_k in constraints C_9 and C_{10} and by substituting the objective of the problem with constraint C_1 , the formulation describes a power minimization problem subject to average delay constraints.

C. Proposed Algorithm

The problem can be solved by any general purpose convex optimization method, following Algorithm 1. A common approach to solve non-linear constrained convex problems is the interior-point method with complexity of roughly $O(N^3)$

[43], where N is the number of variables. For convex problems, the interior-point method converges to a global optimal point with great accuracy. Moreover, in line 4 of Algorithm 1 the initial point of the SCA procedure is updated by the optimal solution obtained from the interior-point method. Therefore, at each iteration, the Taylor approximation is more accurate, since the approximation is closer to the optimal point of (40). Note that the complexity of Algorithm 1 in conjunction with the interior-point method is $O(n_{max} N^3)$, where n_{max} is the maximum number of iterations allowed.

Algorithm 1 Proposed algorithm for delay minimization

- 1: Choose the maximum number of iterations n_{max} , an initial point x_0 , initial points $\theta_{k,0}$, $r_{k,0}$ for the SCA procedure and tolerance ϵ
 - 2: **while** ($n \leq n_{max}$ and $\|x^k - x^{k-1}\|_\infty \geq \epsilon$) **do**
 - 3: solve problem (40) and obtain optimal x^*
 - 4: $x_0 \leftarrow x^*$, $\theta_{k,0} \leftarrow \theta^*$, $\tilde{\mu}_{k,0} \leftarrow \tilde{\mu}_k^*$, $\tilde{f}_{k,0} \leftarrow f^*$
 - 5: **if** $\max\{\frac{L_k}{R_k^*}\} \leq \min\{\frac{1}{\lambda_k}, \frac{X_k L_k}{\tilde{f}_k^*}\}$, $\forall k$ **then**
 - 6: $\tau^* = \max\{\frac{L_k}{R_k^*}\}$
 - 7: **else**
 - 8: Problem is infeasible
 - 9: **end if**
 - 10: **end while**
-

TABLE I: Simulation Parameters

Parameter	Value
N	6
N_0	-174dBm/Hz
L_k	1Mbit
L_p	1
λ_k	0.5 (tasks/sec)
X_k	500 CPU cycles/bit
$f_{max,k}$	1GHz
$P_{max,k}$	0.125W
B_k	1MHz
k_k	10^{-27}
ϵ	10^{-4}
n_{max}	20
d_1, d_2	50m, 100m
α	2.5
n_k	0%, 1%, 2%, 5%

VII. NUMERICAL RESULTS

In this section, simulation results are presented for a GFRA MEC network. Unless otherwise stated, the simulation parameters are given in Table 1. The total number of users N is separated into two clusters. Users of the same cluster have equal path losses Ω_i . The path loss is given by $\Omega_i = \frac{1}{(1+d_i)^\alpha}$, where i is the index of the cluster. In order to extract insights about the network's performance, the optimal resource allocation strategy presented in this section has been evaluated by using Algorithm 1.

In Fig. 3, the offloading strategy and the average delay are plotted against the average task generation of the devices. In Fig. 3a, we observe that for the parameters chosen the local computing delay is by far worse than both the full offloading and the proposed partial scheme. For low average

(a) Average delay

(b) Offloading strategy

Fig. 4: Resource allocation vs the task generation rate

task generation rates, the proposed partial scheme is slightly more efficient than the full offloading. However, as the task generation rate increases the performance gap between the proposed scheme and the full offloading increases as well. Both local computing and full offloading experience congestion that results in greater delays compared to the proposed strategy. It is interesting to note that the delay of the proposed scheme can be 5 times less than the full offloading delay and 20 times less than the local computing delay. The partial scheme will eventually also experience congestion, but for greater values of task generations rate, thus it is much more efficient.

Its efficiency is attributed to the fact that it can adjust the percentage of tasks it transmits to the MEC server or the percentage of tasks that are computed locally. In Fig. 3b the offloading strategy is shown for the same values of λ . Due to the fact that full offloading causes smaller delays in comparison to local computing, for low task generation rates the majority of the tasks are sent to the MEC server. When the rate increases, the probabilistic nature of the transmissions, due to collisions or outage, cannot provide the required queue stability, therefore a percentage of the tasks are eventually computed locally. That decrease in θ is the reason that the partial scheme retains its stability, which can be verified from constraints $C_3 - C_4$ of (24).

In Fig. 4, the impact of the tasks' size is investigated. In

(a) Average delay

(b) Offloading strategy

Fig. 5: Resource allocation vs the task size

Fig. 4a the average delay is illustrated. It is observed that both local computing and full offloading experience congestion for smaller task sizes in comparison to the proposed scheme, which results in increased delays. The partial scheme can be seen to be 4 times better than full offloading and 10 times better than local computing, when both binary strategies experience congestion. The proposed scheme offers a great degree of flexibility, since from this figure and Fig. 3a it is concluded that the partial scheme supports both increased task generation rates and larger task sizes.

In Fig. 4b, the offloading strategy is presented. Note that the task size L does not affect the partial strategy θ directly, as it can be seen from our analysis. The task size has a great impact on the time slot duration, since for collisions to be avoided between successive time slots, a task has to be transmitted to the MEC server in a duration less than a time slot. However, Fig. 4b shows that the task size has a great impact on the offloading strategy, since θ rapidly diminishes for greater values of L . This attributed to the fact that transmitting bigger tasks requires greater data rates R . However, greater data rates cause the outage probability to increase, as can be seen from (2), which undermines the stability of the transmission buffer.

In Fig. 5, the density of the network and its impact on the optimal offloading strategy are studied. As expected, local

(a) Average delay

(b) Offloading strategy

Fig. 6: Resource allocation vs the total number of users

computing delay is constant for all number of users. On the other hand, full offloading experiences congestion for a relatively small number of users, which causes full offloading to be less delay efficient than local computing. This is due to the fact that in a more dense network more clients are likely to transmit data to the MEC server, therefore the probability of collisions increases. The partial scheme is robust under the system's density since it can adjust its partial strategy. As a consequence, the average delay slowly increases with conjunction to the number of users and for 20 users, the delay is about half the delay occurred by utilizing local computing.

Nonetheless, eventually the delay of the partial scheme will gradually approach the delay of the local computing mode, which can also be verified by Fig. 5b, where the offloading factor is shown to rapidly decrease as the number of users increases. A direct consequence of the network's density is also that the users access the channel less frequently, which is necessary for the interference to be regulated.

In Fig. 6, the impact of the distance from the MEC server is examined. In this setup we have assumed that the 1st cluster of users lie in 50m distance from the MEC and the distance of the 2nd cluster is altered. It is observed that the 2nd cluster of users choose to offload a greater amount of tasks to the MEC server compared to the 1st cluster of users which lie

closer to the MEC. At first glance that may seem contradictory. However, because of the greater path loss of the 2nd cluster, its users have to consume more power when offloading their tasks to the MEC server, compared to the users of the 1st cluster. If we take into account the probabilistic offloading scheme, with which some tasks will be offloaded, and other will be locally processed, it is concluded that less power is available to the users of the second cluster, for local computing, which limits the tasks that are locally processed, and therefore, the offloading factor of the 2nd cluster is greater compared to the 1st cluster. Moreover, it should be noted that the users of the 2nd cluster, due to higher outage probability access the channel frequently, causing increased interference to the users of the 1st cluster during the preamble phase.

Furthermore, the offload factor of the 2nd cluster has a non-monotonic behaviour. In general, offloading the tasks to the MEC server is faster than local computing. As the distance increases the users of the 2nd cluster offload their data to the MEC for efficiency and the offload factor increases. However, after some distance, offloading a task to the server is less efficient than locally processing it, therefore the offload factor rapidly diminishes to the point where the users of the 1st cluster offload more tasks than the users of the 2nd cluster.

Regarding the impact of the available preambles on the networks' performance, from Fig. 3-5 it is evident that as the number of preambles increases, the delay diminishes rapidly, due to the fact that the possible collisions are reduced. For an equal number of preambles L_p , the proposed partial framework is more delay efficient as can be seen from the figures depicting the average delay, for $L_p = 1$. From Fig. 5, it is also verified that increasing the number of preambles increases the system's connectivity, since both full and partial offloading, for $L_p = 3$, experience much less congestion compared to the case of $L_p = 1$.

In Fig. 7, the impact of the imperfection between the DT and its underlying physical counterparts is examined. In this setting we have assumed that a constant deviation between the devices' CPU frequency and their DT counterpart exists as in section V. Moreover, due to the unreliability of the wireless channels, the DT is also assumed to have poor knowledge on the hardware configuration of the devices, therefore $\hat{P}_{max,k} = P_{max,k} + n_k$ and $\hat{\lambda}_k = \lambda_k + n_k$. The

Fig. 7: The offloading strategy vs the distance of 2nd cluster

(a) Error percentage vs the number of users

(b) Error percentage vs L

Fig. 8: Deviation impact to the DT delay

imperfection will be expressed as a percentage of the real value of the parameters [37], so for $n_k = 1\%$, $\hat{\lambda}_k = \lambda_k \pm \frac{1}{100} \lambda_k$, etc. From Fig. 7a it is observed that a slight uncertainty between the DT and the physical system causes greater errors to the optimal resource allocation as the number of users increases. Therefore, an imperfection tends to be more damaging as the size of the physical space and the DT increase. Moreover, in Fig. 7b the percentage of error caused with various task sizes is plotted. The error increases as the task size increases. Consequently, inaccuracies between the DT and the physical network cannot be ignored when the state of the network approaches congestion. Those imperfections might cause significant errors under computationally demanding network states, for example excessive traffic of packet generation.

In Fig. 8, the convergence of Algorithm 1 is shown. More users in the network indicate a larger number of constraints and optimization variables. By choosing a random point, which satisfies the stability constraints, and for the case of 2 users, it is shown that the algorithm slowly converges with accuracy of approximately $5 * 10^{-2}$ within 20 iterations. However, for the case of 6 users the algorithm needs 5 iterations to converge with accuracy lower than 10^{-4} . Moreover, for 12 users, only 4 iterations are needed. The fact that the warm start approach is used between the iterations greatly accelerates the

Fig. 9: Convergence of Algorithm I

proposed algorithm. Therefore, a good strategy for choosing the initial point is to run the algorithm for a small and easy problem, for example for the 2 users case, and then, the optimal point found is utilized as the initial point for other cases.

VIII. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we studied the average delay for a DT-aided MEC system with GF random access by using queueing theory tools. A novel partial offloading scheme was proposed in which a task is probabilistically either computed locally or sent to the MEC server. The duration of the data transmission phase, an arbitrary number of preambles and the average outage probability were taken into account, while an adaptive data transmission rate was utilized. Then, closed-form relations were extracted for the average delay of each device and an optimization aiming to minimize the average delay of all users was formulated by utilizing SCA and AO. Finally, simulation results were presented which give insights about the network's resource allocation strategy under different scenarios. The impact of the network density, the available preambles, the distance from the MEC server, the task size and the average task generation rate were examined and it was shown that the proposed scheme can efficiently adjust its partial strategy to avoid congestion. Finally, the impact of an imperfect DT was examined. Future works could aim to study semi-GF access with NOMA for MEC, or to further investigate the dynamic characteristics of the DT-MEC architecture and the case of stochastic and unknown imperfections between the DT and the physical world.

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